

Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp

OSCARS grant proposal for the first open call. The project was funded with project start date 01.01.2025.

OSPARK website:

<https://oscars-project.eu/projects/ospark-bootcamp-open-science-promotion-and-advocacy-research-knowledge-bootcamp>

Project Partners

Digital Research Academy and OLS.

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Project Public Summary

The Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) project aims to develop a comprehensive training program implemented in a multi-week bootcamp to empower members of the OSCARS Science Clusters and the broader Open Science community with evidence-based marketing and communication skills. By equipping participants with these essential skills, the project seeks to **enhance visibility of ESFRIs and other Research Infrastructures (RIs) while supporting Open Science advocates to share their message**. The wealth of resources offered by researchers and research support infrastructures is challenged by an awareness gap among their potential users. We will bridge this gap by training potential "multipliers" to effectively promote their projects, activities and services, fostering a culture of openness, equity and collaboration within the research community. We practise openness by making the developed curriculum and all other outputs openly available according to FAIR principles and under an open licence (generally CC-BY 4.0).

ADVOCATE

CONTENT + MEDIUM

TARGET AUDIENCE

The curriculum includes foundational principles of evidence-based marketing, using modern media, content creation, and outreach team work. We discuss and practice engaging in outreach formats beyond the scientific paper such as videos, science slams or social media, with a focus on what works for which target audience. Although our efforts focus mainly on communicating within a broader context, we will also take a look at creating visibility and awareness within an institution or project. Throughout the bootcamp, we will discuss case studies and support participants in practically implementing the new skills in their day-to-day work. Outreach, marketing, and communication can be seen as scary or difficult. We want to make it as effortless and enjoyable as possible for the Research Infrastructures and Open Science advocates who participate in our training.

Our approach to developing the training is community-based, agile and based on scientific evidence. The communities who are to benefit from the bootcamps contribute both their wishes as well as their knowledge. Many of the RIs and Open Science initiatives already have done great work that can serve as case studies. Our agile project plan ensures that we build incrementally better training, while ensuring to implement useful training, which can be evaluated and improved sooner rather than later. Not only these early training instances, but also a literature review on the scientific evidence will help us determine the most effective strategies in marketing and communication for Open Science purposes.

This project has the potential to dramatically increase the visibility and thus effectiveness of Open Science initiatives, including the RIs, the science clusters, EOSC-funded projects, grass-roots communities and more. We don't only train them in marketing and outreach,

but as part of the bootcamp develop a full-fledged marketing and outreach strategy with them. This will result in projects, activities, or services that previously no-one had heard of becoming thriving and popular resources that researchers and research staff *want* to engage with.

By sharing the learning materials and supporting data in a FAIR way, not only participants in our bootcamp can use the wealth of knowledge we will build in this project, but anyone can reuse them to learn from them, update them, or adjust them for further purposes. This will help to ensure that Open Science initiatives get the tools and visibility they need and deserve.

Project description

This project will develop a training program and bootcamp to support and empower members of the OSCARS Science Clusters and general Open Science community with skills in evidence-based marketing and communication. This will enhance participants' ongoing efforts to create visibility of the mission and services of ESFRIs and other RIs, as well as increasing the influence of Open Science community members in their immediate environments and beyond. We expect that the final program will consist of 6-8 learning sessions, followed by a two-day in-person "bootcamp".

This program is essential to **bridge the gap between the valuable resources offered by Open Science initiatives and infrastructures and the research staff who stand to benefit from them** (see also Figure 1, supplementary material). Despite the abundance of services and support available, these infrastructures often struggle to effectively advertise their offerings, leading to a significant disconnect between availability and awareness. We can address this issue by equipping individuals from RIs with the tools and strategies to effectively promote themselves, their research, and the services offered by the RIs. This proactive approach not only enhances the visibility and utilisation of existing resources but also fosters a culture of openness and collaboration within the research community, ultimately advancing the goals of Open Science.

Moreover, beyond merely raising awareness of existing RI resources, this evidence-based marketing and communication bootcamp holds potential to empower research staff to become **internal Open Science advocates** at their institutes. With the skills and mindset necessary to effectively promote Open Science principles, the program can catalyse the needed cultural shift towards openness and collaboration within the research community, leading to greater access, equity and scientific progress for society. By fostering a cadre of informed and proactive advocates, the program **extends its impact externally** beyond individual institutions, contributing to the collective effort to democratise access to research and accelerate scientific progress.

Our approach to developing the training is community-based, agile and based on scientific evidence.

We **co-create the curriculum with the communities** who are to benefit from the bootcamp. They contribute their wishes, needs and knowledge. Many of them have already done outreach work that can serve as case studies, such as the PaNOSC training catalogue PaN-Training.eu website, the [ESCAPE citizen science](#) work, or the [ELIXIR RDMBites](#).

We implement training in an agile fashion, which means that we use **iterative project management techniques** (see Figure 2, supplementary materials), in order to provide useful training fast, iterating and improving it over time to grow the full bootcamp material. We start out with planning and developing a short - yet already useful - training pilot that we deliver to an initial group, who can benefit from the materials. After evaluating the pilot, we move on to **planning, developing, delivering and evaluating an increasingly holistic training program, up to the full bootcamp**.

As well as evaluating our early training instances, we will perform literature review on the **scientific evidence on marketing, “influencing”, psychology, and outreach** to help us determine the most effective strategies in marketing and communication for Open Science purposes. Hence, our bootcamp will not only be thoroughly developed from a training standpoint but will also contain evidence-based marketing methods that have been shown to reach their goal. Using these techniques for a cause we believe in - Open Science - is what inspires us in this project.

Although the contents of the training will be co-created with the community, we want to showcase a few topic areas that we believe may be useful as part of the bootcamp. Please note these will develop and change based on our iterative, community-driven and evidence-based process.

Potential Topics:

Foundations of Outreach and Marketing

- Why outreach and marketing matter
- Understanding your goals and target audiences
- Strategies to make your message relevant and relatable
- Viewing marketing as a way to provide value
- Leveraging evidence-based marketing
- Differences in internal and external communication
- FAIR includes Findable - marketing for FAIR research outputs

Formats beyond the paper

- Exploring outreach formats: websites, blogs, videos, social media posts, podcasts, networking, talks, newsletters, science slams, ...
- Overview on social media - platforms, etiquette, and more
- Thinking outside the box - how to create awareness in unconventional ways

Creating content that works

- What works for you? - Developing first content bites
- Evaluating your content
- How being yourself can help you reach more people
- Helping and providing value rather than showing off
- Telling stories
- Creating visual and audio content

Marketing as a team effort

- Developing an integrated marketing communications strategy
- Coordinating messaging across various communication channels
- Keeping creativity while making sure the message is appropriate
- Consistent branding and design

Throughout the bootcamp, there will be **case studies, workshops, and hands-on practicals** tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities faced by research support infrastructures. Participants will gain practical skills and knowledge to effectively promote their services, engage with researchers, and advance their mission within the scientific community. Bootcamp participants will develop a full-fledged marketing and outreach strategy. This will result in projects, activities, or services that previously no-one had heard of becoming thriving and popular resources that researchers and research staff *want* to engage with.

The final program will consist of 6-8 learning sessions, followed by a two-day in-person "bootcamp". Depending on findings in the pilot training and early iterations of our agile training development, this may change and asynchronous or flipped-classroom style materials may be used additionally to the online and in-person sessions. Early training iterations and pilots will have differing formats, depending on the optimal format to evaluate the training while providing value to the participants.

Materials - such as slides, example content, or websites - developed as part of this project will be made openly available as **FAIR materials under an open licence** (generally CC-BY 4.0). By sharing the learning materials in a FAIR way, not only participants in our bootcamp can use the wealth of knowledge we will build in this project, but anyone can reuse them to learn from them, update them, or adjust them for further purposes. Such that all Open Science initiatives get the tools and visibility they need and deserve.

The **project partners** bring together their expertise in creating effective and interactive

training experiences to create the training program.

OLS (<https://we-are-ols.org/>, formerly Open Life Science) is a not-for-profit organisation dedicated to equitable global culture change in research, towards open community-driven principles. The organisational three pillars are **Open Science mentoring and training** for individuals and teams worldwide, evidence-based **research** for widening participation in research, and open **incubation** that provides hands-on support for further development of Open Science projects stemming from their mentoring programs. Notable Open Science projects nurtured in OLS include: [FAIR Phytoliths - increasing the FAIRness of phytoliths data](#) and the [Euro-Biolmaging Scientific Ambassadors program](#). The Executive Director and co-founder of OLS, Dr. Yo Yehudi (<https://yo-yehudi.com/>) transitioned OLS from a 100% volunteer labor initiative to a grant-funded organization with over 600 community members across 6 continents and 60+ countries worldwide, running virtual online Open Science cohorts for five years. OLS cohort graduates have gone on to receive Grants and Fellowships from The Lacuna Fund, EOSC-Life, Code for Science and Society, The Software Sustainability Institute, The Open Bioinformatics Foundation, The Awesome Foundation, and more.

The **Digital Research Academy** (DRA, <https://digital-research.academy/>) is an international network of trainers that provides **customised training** with the aim of **improving the quality of research**. The expertises in the trainer network spans three broad categories: **Open Science, data literacy, and research software engineering**. The DRA is led by co-founders **Dr. Heidi Seibold** and **Dr. Joyce Kao, EMBA** with a combined experience of over 25 years in Open Science, community building, scientific research, teaching, and project management. Dr. Seibold (<https://heidiseibold.com/>) is a consultant for open and reproducible data science with extensive experience designing inclusive interactive courses, workshops and events. She has launched two podcasts series examining topics in reshaping academia ([>reboot academia](#)) and Open Science ([Open Science Stories](#)). Dr. Kao (<https://www.jykao.com/>) is a consultant for open innovation, digitalization and project management. She is also the founder of the [Open Innovation in Life Sciences association](#) that promotes Open Science practices among early career researchers through organising Open Science focused event programs and empowering ECR organisers with skills in project management, business development, and marketing. Next to her involvement in the DRA, **Melanie Imming** has +15 years experience in helping leading academic organisations develop their engagement strategy around topics such as Open Science and FAIR data. Melanie is experienced in branding campaigns and developing concepts like the annual National Open Science Festival in the Netherlands. She is a member of the executive team of the grass-roots [Open Science Communities](#) and has participated in 12+ EU projects, often focusing on stakeholder engagement and creating impact.

Scientific impacts

Our contribution is designed to ensure that the open scientific knowledge and infrastructures developed by RIs becomes findable, and is correctly pitched to reach target audiences. Overall, our goal is to increase efficiency and effectiveness of research, meaning there is less reinventing and fragmentation, and instead more re-use and

collaboration on existing resources,

Whilst scientists and researchers are routinely trained to write highly technical papers about in-depth, robust research, academic writing and incentives are not always well-aligned with systemic change. This is evidenced in many ways throughout research and the world more generally. In science, a researcher's career is assessed by non-scientific measures like the impact factor and number of publications a researcher produces. Across society, climate change is treated as a "question" rather than an evidence-based truth. There is a genuine gap between the creation of knowledge and the implementation of behaviours based on this knowledge. Put more simply: **Just because a researcher can robustly prove something is true does not mean they can convince others that it is true.**

However, achieving real-world change and influencing others is a well known art and science practised and understood in many different domains, often by different names. Marketers, user experience researchers, and psychologists understand how to influence individuals to purchase items, or to nudge people to choose a preferred option from multiple different products [\[1\]](#), [\[2\]](#), [\[3\]](#). Policy advocates digest evidence-based articles into one and two-page executive briefs that a politician has time to read. Meanwhile, politicians and demagogues use the power of personality and emotion to persuade people to follow their political goals, and influencers create digestible social media content that attracts the eyes of thousands or even millions.

Science Communicators (SciComm) make scientific concepts approachable and even exciting for a lay-person. Notable examples include Mai Thi Nguyen-Kim [\[4\]](#), Neil deGrasse Tyson [\[5\]](#), Elizabeth Bik [\[6\]](#), Zoe Ayres [\[7\]](#), and many others [\[8\]](#).

We propose to **expand the scientific state-of-the-art** broadly, by capacity-building amongst researchers to increase the influence of their work. All the different change-makers above have differing techniques, many of which are well-studied and understood. Our proposal will draw from all these domains, embracing citizen science communicators, influencers, digital marketers and social media gurus, as well as the evidence base from Open Science meta research, psychology, and social behavioural research. This will also allow us to create links and shared knowledge between these disparate communities and the ~2500-strong communities of DRA, OLS, and their networks. We expect impact to become evident from the co-creation stage of WP 2, but additionally to grow over time as we trial and refine our training modules based on feedback from participants and creators.

We attach **letters of support from collaborators** who will help us reach this level of impact. In the [life sciences](#), we have support from: ELIXIR-UK, including 28 node member organisations and €10k of in-kind promotion support; and from OILS (Open Innovation in Life Sciences) and Euro-BioImaging ERIC committing to promote and re-use our training. In [photon/neutron sources-based experimental research](#), we have support commitment to pilot the training from HZDR as a PaNOSC training consortium member, and in computer science we have in-kind staff support and network promotion from the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI). The SSI is also a participating member of the EVERSE project (<https://everse.software/>), which is creating a framework for research

software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities, and building a European network of Research Software Quality. In addition, we engage with libraries as a research infrastructure via commitment from Cologne University and City Library to participate in the bootcamp, who are a part of several national and EU consortiums and networks (i.e. C3RDM, NFDI4Health, EUniWell, Open Science Centre Cologne).

Organisationally, this consortium has ties with existing clusters across Europe and the UK, but we also extend our work globally, as our community spreads across not just Europe and North America, but also with researchers in Saudi Arabia, Nepal, Mali, Iraq, Cameroon, Nigeria, South Africa, India, Egypt, Turkey, Kenya, Japan, Uganda, South Korea, Australia, Eswatini, and other areas as well.

Assessment: In order to understand our impact and ensure that we iterate on our work to achieve the objectives of increased visibility of the services of ESFRIs and other RIs and increasing the influence of Open Science community members, we will involve a Resident Fellow based at OLS. This Fellow will be responsible for designing and implementing a feedback survey, building on previous work carried out by OLS to qualitatively (peer-reviewed reflexive interview study; currently in final stages of analysis) and quantitatively (<https://openlifesci.org/ols-stats/>) assess their open science training program. Feedback periods will be spaced evenly across the two years, culminating in a final impact report at the end of the grant activities (D4.2).

Future impact: Longer term, we foresee that this work could move individuals and organisations from influencing at smaller scales to more national or international scales, e.g. public policy at a governmental or EU level. By ensuring our training resources are deposited FAIRly and openly as both scholarly outputs and digestible training courses, we will enable re-use and building upon / extending our work in the future.

- [1] S. C. Whitley, R. Trudel, and D. Kurt, 'The Influence of Purchase Motivation on Perceived Preference Uniqueness and Assortment Size Choice', *J. Consum. Res.*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 710–724, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1093/jcr/ucy031.
- [2] C. M. Gray, Y. Kou, B. Battles, J. Hoggatt, and A. L. Toombs, 'The Dark (Patterns) Side of UX Design', in *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, in CHI '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Apr. 2018, pp. 1–14. doi: 10.1145/3173574.3174108.
- [3] A. Mathur *et al.*, 'Dark Patterns at Scale: Findings from a Crawl of 11K Shopping Websites', *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.*, vol. 3, no. CSCW, p. 81:1-81:32, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1145/3359183.
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- [5] 'Neil deGrasse Tyson', *Wikipedia*. May 12, 2024. Accessed: May 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Neil_deGrasse_Tyson&oldid=1223553177
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- [7] 'Zoë J. Ayres | Mental Health in Academia', Zoë J Ayres. Accessed: May 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.zjayres.com>
- [8] 'Top 70 Science Influencers in 2024', FeedSpot for Influencers. Accessed: May 14,

2024. [Online].
https://influencers.feedspot.com/science_instagram_influencers/

Available:

Digital resources

As our project focuses on developing a training bootcamp, the main materials we create and reuse are learning materials, which we will make available as FAIR Open Educational Resources (OER).

The project will contribute to digital resources by creating OERs for the training bootcamp. The curriculum and learning resources (slides, visuals, etc) will be uploaded and shared on a trusted repository federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements (e.g. Zenodo, etc.) according to the FAIR principles and under an open licence (generally CC-BY 4.0).

If appropriate, any community/audience-specific content generated within the curriculum will be encouraged to be released with open licences and also uploaded on domain-relevant open repositories and platforms (e.g. Zenodo, OSF, EOSC Future Knowledge Hub, etc.). This approach enables other communities within and external to the Science Clusters to adapt and implement similar bootcamps tailored to their specific needs, thereby amplifying messages within and beyond their respective domains.

Recordings of training videos, slides, and speaker names will be hosted online in OLS's open science training video library (<https://openlifesci.org/openseeds/library.html>) as well as being cross-deposited to other appropriate repositories mentioned above.

Our approach involves curating and repurposing existing digital resources content. For example, it is intended to reuse the training material on creating high-quality video content developed as a part of another EU project, [EUniWell](#), as part of their FAIR Data Training component. Additional sources where we can reuse training content include the EVERSE training initiative (<https://everse.software/>), videos from ELIXIR RDMBites (<https://fellowship.elixiruknode.org/>) and ELIXIR TeSS (<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>), etc. By incorporating existing materials into our curriculum, we leverage the expertise and resources already available within the community, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

In terms of computing resources, we will require robust infrastructure to support the development and dissemination of training materials, and hosting of virtual sessions. We anticipate this will be achieved using existing infrastructure, such as cloud-based platforms for content creation and delivery, as well as computing resources for data analysis and visualisation exercises.

Additionally, we will use collaborative GDPR-friendly tools for remote learning and communication to facilitate interactions among participants and instructors (e.g. Zoom, Miro, Mattermost, etc.). Participant management for each iteration of the bootcamp will be achieved through the Indico event management platform hosted by DRA (events.digital-research.academy).

Project Implementation, Budget Breakdown and Final Deliverables

WP1: Co-creation of OSPARK Bootcamp Program (Allocated Budget (AB): €90,405.03)

The Co-Creation process of the training bootcamp involves a collaborative effort between the project team and the intended audience to ensure the program meets their specific needs and requirements. The first task (M1-M6) includes refining target audience/user personas and assessing the needs and fit of the program by conducting stakeholder consultations, and reviewing relevant literature on outreach education. Through stakeholder consultations, the project team engages with representatives from research support infrastructures, OSCARS Science Clusters, and the broader Open Science community to gather insights and feedback on the proposed training program. Additionally, literature reviews on influencer and marketing education provide valuable insights into best practices and emerging trends in the field. Based on these inputs and feedback from three iterative implementations, the program curriculum is co-planned and co-developed (M7-M18), ensuring that it addresses the unique challenges and opportunities faced by RIs in the Science Clusters. By involving the intended audience in the Co-Creation process, the training bootcamp is tailored to their specific needs, ultimately enhancing its effectiveness and relevance. The initial curriculum will be ready in M12 (MS3) leading to the completion of the final curriculum in M18 (MS5, D1.2).

WP2: Iterative implementation & impact assessment (AB: €80,479.38)

The iterative implementation and impact assessment process of the training bootcamp is structured to ensure continuous improvement and effectiveness of the program. This work package encompasses several key tasks, including delivery of three iterative implementations of the bootcamp (M10-M21), and ongoing assessment of its impact (M6, M15, M23) regarding new skills gained by participants to aid the acceleration of the uptake of RI and EOSC resources (data, services, policies, interoperability framework, etc.). This iterative approach allows for real-time adjustments to the program content, format, and delivery methods based on participant feedback and observed outcomes. The first iteration (MS4) is aimed to be completed in M15 and the final iteration (MS6) in M21. Ongoing impact assessment activities are conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the program in achieving its objectives and effect on the research community.

WP3: Communication, Dissemination, & Sustainability (AB: €25,699.87)

This WP ensures the wide-reaching impact and long-term integration into existing Open Science initiatives. The tasks within this work package include devising a communication and dissemination strategy plan to be included in the final report (D4.2), along with its implementation (M1-M18), to effectively promote the bootcamp program to the target audience and stakeholders and release the deliverables as FAIR OERs on the EOSC Future Knowledge Hub/Exchange or other trusted repositories (i.e. Zenodo, OSF, etc.). This strategy plan for the promotion of the bootcamp (MS2 - ready by M6) encompasses various communication channels and tactics to maximise visibility and engagement, including social media campaigns, newsletters, website promotion, and targeted outreach to relevant communities. Additionally, we will integrate the bootcamp program into existing OLS and DRA activities (M17-M24) aligning with and complementing our ongoing activities. We will make it easy for other initiatives to reuse and adapt the materials for their purposes. Through strategic communication, dissemination, and

sustainable integration efforts, WP3 aims to maximise the reach and impact of the bootcamp program, ultimately contributing to the advancement of Open Science principles and practices on a larger scale.

WP4: Management and Coordination (AB: €20,772.84) The final work package of the project focuses on the management and coordination of various aspects to ensure the smooth execution and success of the initiative. This includes the coordination of supporting infrastructure to facilitate the implementation of the bootcamp program effectively. This project will be kicked off in a Kickoff Meeting (MS1) in the first month. By managing logistical details, resource allocation, and coordination among project partners, this work package ensures seamless collaboration and communication throughout the project duration. Additionally, the management team is responsible for the final reporting (D4.2), budget management, and overseeing the Resident Fellow,, ensuring transparency, accountability, and efficient use of project resources.

Total budget breakdown (detailed breakdown in PDF supplement)

- Total personnel costs: €170,939.24
- Travel costs: €8,700.00
- Other goods, works, and services: €37,718.00
- Indirect costs (15%): €32,603.59

Expected results and timeline (detailed breakdown in PDF supplement)

	Mid project results (by M12)	End project results (by M24)
WP1	MS3 - Initial program curriculum ready (M12)	MS5 - Final program curriculum ready, D1.2 Program Curriculum (M18)
WP2		MS4- First implementation completed (M15), MS6 - Final implementation completed (M21)
WP3	MS2-Communication & Dissemination Strategy Plan ready (M6)	
WP4	MS1-Kickoff Meeting held (M1)	D4.2-Final Project Report (M24)

All deliverables will be publicly disseminated and data/content generated from them will be deposited in a trusted repository federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements.

D1.2 Program Curriculum - Description of the Program curriculum along with the co-creation methods used to create the curriculum.

D4.2 Final Project Report (including Presentation) - Contains three parts: 1. A *final project summary in PDF format of maximum 5000 characters, including spaces*. 2. A "scientific journal or journal-type" article summarising the main project results including impact assessment and methodology used to achieve them. 3. A presentation on the

impact and results of the project.

Grant stages

						Year 1				Year 2				Deliverables/ Milestones
WP	WP Title	WP Lead	Task Lead	Task	Task Description	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
1	Co-creation of OSPARK Training Bootcamp Program	DRA	OLS	1.1	Requirements collection of target audiences and information collection of state of the art on influencer/marketing education									
			DRA	1.2	Program curriculum development						M2, D1.2			
2	Iterative implementation & assessment of impact	OLS	OLS	2.1	Iterative implementation of program and feedback collection					M3		M4		M3- First implementation started, M4 - Final implementation started
			OLS	2.2	Assessment of impact (ongoing and future)								D2.2	
3	Communication, Dissemination, & Sustainability	DRA	OLS	3.1	Communication and dissemination strategy plan & implementation		M5							M5-Strategy plan ready
			OLS	3.2	Sustainable integration into existing OLS And DRA activities									
4	Management and Coordination	OLS	OLS	4.1	Coordination of supporting infrastructure	M1								M1-Kickoff Meeting held
			OLS	4.2	Reporting, budget & fellowships management								D4.2	

Initial notes created for the proposal

